

Document Content

This document describes the types of files available in the RADx Data Hub and a workflow for deciding which files to use for secondary analysis.

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Introduction

The RADx Data Hub is a file-based repository for COVID-19 testing data collected by [RADx programs](#) as part of the [NIH Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics \(RADx\) Initiative](#). This document describes the various types of files hosted in the RADx Data Hub and their relationship to each other.

In the RADx Data Hub, files are grouped into three main categories: (1) study documents that provide additional details and context to allow the appropriate use of study data, (2) data files that contain data derived from studies, and (3) files that contain metadata that describe data files and their contents.

It is highly recommended that researchers view data dictionaries and study documents in addition to the data files to interpret the data accurately.

Study Documents

Study documents may include, but are not limited to, study protocols, data collection forms, or README files provided by study staff. **Reviewing study documents is essential for accurate data interpretation and proper usage.**

- Study Protocols: Describe the study design, methodology, and inclusion/exclusion criteria.

- Data Collection Forms: Provide details on how data were recorded (e.g., structure, variables).
- README Files: Explain dataset-specific considerations, including unique coding decisions.

Data Files

In the RADx Data Hub data are harmonized, or re-labeled and re-coded, so data can be uniformly interpreted across multiple studies. All data files contain de-identified data.

Most studies provide two types of data files:

- **Harmonized files** ([transformcopy](#))
- **Non-harmonized files** ([origcopy](#))

The difference between an origcopy file and a transformcopy file is harmonization of RADx Core Variables, also called RADx Tier I Common Data Elements (RADx Tier I CDEs). RADx Core Variables:

- Describe human study data, for example, symptoms, conditions and demographics.
- Are required by human subject RADx studies.
- Ensure users can access these variables consistently across all RADx projects to compare data across studies.

Non-harmonized files ([origcopy](#)) are files containing data ready for analysis by Data Hub users but that have not been harmonized across RADx programs, but may be harmonized within an individual RADx program. In contrast, the *Harmonized files* described below contain harmonized RADx Core Variables.

Harmonized files ([transformcopy](#)) are files containing data that have been harmonized with respect to the harmonization rules in the [RADx Global Codebook](#). They are derived from origcopy files by applying said harmonization rules and replacing each blank value with a RADx Missing Value code from [RADx Tiger Team Missing Value Reasons](#), which specifies the reason for its absence.

Precise details of how data files are structured and the relationship between origcopy and transformcopy files are described in [RADx Data File Naming Conventions and Content Rules for Data Submitters](#).

Example Decision Flow for Data File Selection

The following workflow provides guidance to researchers in selecting which data file(s) to use for secondary analysis. This workflow is an example. **Each researcher should explore all data files provided to them to determine which variables and files are most appropriate.** If you have questions, fill out a [Support Request](#) to connect with the RADx Data Hub Partners.

Step 1: Do the study data files include both **origcopy and **transformcopy**?**

- NO: Use the **origcopy** file.
- YES: Proceed to Step 2.

Step 2: Is your analysis exclusively focused on non-human study data (e.g., wastewater data)?

Non-human study data are only in **origcopy** files.

- YES: Use the **origcopy** file.
- NO: Proceed to Step 3.

Step 3: Will your analysis include data from a single program only (e.g., only RADx-UP, RADx-rad, or RADx Tech)?

Variables are uniformly used across all studies within any given program. When focusing on a specific program the use of harmonized data (transformcopy files) is unnecessary.

- YES: Use the **origcopy** file.
- NO: Proceed to Step 4.

Step 4: Does your analysis include data from RADx Tech studies?

- NO: Use the **transformcopy** file.

- YES: Proceed to Step 5.

Step 5: Do you require more detailed information on Hispanic origin available in RADx Tech human studies?

- YES: Use **both** file types:
 - **origcopy** files for **RADx Tech**.
 - **transformcopy** files for other programs.Note: Be prepared to address differences in granularity between the **RADx Tech ethnicity** variable and the **RADx-UP/RADx-rad nih_ethnicity** variable.
- NO: Use the **transformcopy** files.

Metadata and Data Dictionary Files

RADx data files are accompanied by metadata and data dictionary files that describe the content, structure, and context of the data. The metadata files are composed using the **RADx Metadata Specification**, which provides a standardized framework for representing data attributes and ensuring consistency across studies.

RADx Metadata Specification

The **RADx Metadata Specification** defines the structure and content of metadata files. It standardizes how files are described, enabling consistent interpretation across studies. A core component of this specification—specific to **RADx-UP studies**—is the **Data Characteristics Summary**. The **Data Characteristics Summary** provides high-level statistical profiles of key demographic, clinical, and behavioral variables within RADx-UP datasets.

Metadata Files:

The META file contains metadata about the data file itself, such as information about who created it, when it was created, and other file-specific details. This file is formatted as a JSON-LD and can be viewed using the embedded viewer in the Data Hub or downloaded for processing with standard JSON tools.

Data Dictionary Files:

The DICT file contains metadata about the variables (columns) in the data file. It is provided as a Comma Separated Values (CSV) file and is intended to be read as-is. This file is vital for understanding the meaning of the variables and interpreting the data accurately.

The [RADx Data Dictionary File Specification](#) outlines the details of data dictionary files.

File Relationships

Files are often linked together by file naming conventions. For example, if a study has produced some data under the title “Xyz”, the RADx Data Hub contains at least the first three files as shown in the table below. If the study involves human participants and provides RADx Core Variables, these will have been harmonized in accordance with the RADx Global Code Book. In this case, the study will also contain transformcopy files as shown in the last three rows of the table below.

File Name	Category	Related to File
Xyz_DATA_origcopy.csv	Data (non-harmonized)	-
Xyz_META_origcopy.json	Metadata	Xyz_DATA_origcopy.csv
Xyz_DICT_origcopy.csv	Metadata	Xyz_DATA_origcopy.csv
Xyz_DATA_transformcopy.csv	Data (harmonized)	Xyz_DATA_origcopy.csv
Xyz_META_transformcopy.json	Metadata	Xyz_DATA_transformcopy.csv
Xyz_DICT_transformcopy.csv	Metadata	Xyz_DATA_transformcopy.csv